

DEVELOPMENT STUDY OF LIGHTWEIGHT STRUCTURAL MATERIALS USING UD CARBON NANOTUBE SHEET

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1 General Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have great mechanical, thermal and electrical properties [1-3]. They are believed to be promising candidates as reinforcement for the next generation of high performance structural composites. CNTs were discovered in 1991 [4] and can be classified into single-walled CNT (SWCNT) and multi-walled CNT (MWCNT) [5]. Significant efforts have been focused on developing CNT composites over the last two decades.

Studies of CNT composites so far have largely focused on improving the nanotube dispersion quality with the matrix. To achieve good quality CNT dispersion in polymer, short CNTs reinforced polymer composites with low volume fractions are typically utilized [6-7]. Although short CNT composites have some improvements in certain low volume fraction applications, such as thermally and electrically conducting materials, but their mechanical properties fall far short of traditional high performance carbon fiber reinforced composites, since achieving high volume fractions of dispersed CNTs in polymer is highly difficult.

In a recent research of Inoue et al. [8], vertically aligned CNTs were synthesized on a smooth quartz substrate using a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method. The uni-directional (UD) horizontally aligned nanotube sheet was drawn from vertically aligned CNT array onto a rotating spool [9-11]. By using this CNT sheet, a high volume fraction of highly aligned CNTs was expected to be dispersed in polymer.

In this study, three-phase laminated composites based on UD horizontally aligned CNT sheets and carbon fiber (CF)/ epoxy resin prepreg was studied to demonstrate the possibility of the use of UD carbon nanotube sheet as a reinforcement of lightweight structural materials. Micro structures of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites were observed using the optical microscope and the FE-Scanning electron microscope (SEM). The mechanical properties for these composites were evaluated by tensile test. CNT volume fraction was estimated by thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA).

2 Experimental methods

2.1 Processing of UD CNT sheets

The CNTs array which was synthesized on a quartz substrate by CVD method was shown in Fig.1. By picking CNTs web on the end of array, CNTs were continuously drawn and wound on a rotating spool (Fig. 2). Fig. 2 shows the processing of CNT sheet by drawing and winding on a rotating cylindrical spool. The CNT sheets with 50 plies were drawn from CNT arrays for composite fabrication. Fig. 3 shows SEM micrograph of CNTs and image of CNT sheet. Diameter and length of the CNTs were about 50-60 nm and 1 mm, respectively.

2.2 Fabricating composite materials

Various CF/CNT/epoxy resin composite materials were fabricated by covering the UD CNT sheets on the both sides of CF/epoxy resin prepreg and cured in vacuum autoclave at 180°C under 0.5 MPa for 4 hours. Fig. 4 shows the schemes for processing of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites. For fabrication of

CF(-0°)/CNT/epoxy resin composites, UD CNT sheets with 100, 200 and 300 plies were placed in the same direction (0 degree) with CF. Meanwhile, UD CNT sheets with 100, 200 and 300 plies were placed in perpendicular direction (90 degree) with CF to fabricate CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composites.

Fig. 1 FE-SEM image of CNT arrays

Fig. 2 Drawing UD CNT sheet

(a) SEM image of CNT sheet

(b) Picture of UD CNT sheet

Fig. 3 UD carbon nanotube sheet

2.3 Micro structure observation

Cross-sections of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composite materials were polished. The cross-sections of the composites were observed by optical microscope.

The fracture surfaces of these materials were observed using the FE-SEM (SU8030, Hitachi Corp., Tokyo, Japan).

(a) CF(-0°)/CNT/epoxy resin composite materials

(b) CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composite materials

Fig. 4 Schemes for processing of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites

2.4 Tensile test

Tensile specimens were cut out from CF/CNT/epoxy composite sheets. The both clamped ends of the specimens (Fig. 5) were glued by two glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) tabs. Strain gauges were glued at the center of the specimens to measure the fracture strain. Fig. 5(a) shows the shape and dimension of two types of tensile specimens for CF-0°/CNT/epoxy resin composites. Meantime, two kinds of tensile specimens for CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composites were indicated in Fig. 5(b). To measure the difference of elastic modulus of CF/epoxy resin part and CF/CNT/epoxy resin part, strain gauges were also glued on CF/epoxy resin parts in both ends of the specimens as shown in Fig.5. The longer specimens were for measuring both elastic modulus of CF/epoxy resin part and CF/CNT/epoxy resin part at the same time. The shorter specimens were in order to be fractured near CF/CNT/epoxy resin part. All the tensile tests were carried out at RT with a crosshead speed of 0.05 mm/min in the CNT direction using Shimadzu Autograph AG-5000A.

Fig. 5 Tensile test specimens

2.5 Thermo gravimetric analysis

About 20 mg composite material samples were heat-treated using the thermo gravimetric analyzer (TGA-50, Shimadzu Corp., Japan). The temperature was kept at 1000°C for 20 minutes in argon gas to remove matrix. The volume fractions were calculated by the weight change before and after the TGA.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Cross-sectional morphology and thickness

Figure 6 shows typical cross-sectional micrographs of investigated composite materials. In the case of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composite (Fig. 6b), epoxy resin layer on upper and lower parts of CF/epoxy resin layer are observed in comparison with CF/epoxy resin composite (Fig. 6a). This implies that epoxy resin from CF/epoxy resin prepreg filled CNT sheets layer to form CNT/epoxy resin composite. In the case of CF-90°/CNTs/epoxy resin composites (Fig. 6c), sides of CF and epoxy resin layer are observed. This indicates that these composite materials were composed of CF/epoxy resin layer and CNT/epoxy resin layers. Table 1 shows thicknesses of composite and each layer. When increasing the CNT plies total thickness of the composite and the thickness of CNT/epoxy resin layers increased, but the thickness of CF/epoxy resin layer decreased. This can be explained that the CNT sheets absorbed much epoxy resin in the prepreg when increasing the CNT plies.

3.2 Morphologies of fracture surface

Figure 7 shows FE-SEM fracture surface images of CF/ CNTs/epoxy resin composite with 300 CNT plies. As seen in Fig. 7 the upper layer is CF/epoxy resin composite, while the lower layer is CNT/epoxy resin composite. In CNT/epoxy resin layer, lots of CNTs are observed. This confirmed again that the composite materials were composed of CF/epoxy resin layer in the middle and CNT/epoxy resin layers in upper and lower parts.

Fig. 6 Cross-sectional morphologies of investigated composites

Table 1 Thickness of the composites and layers

	Thickness [mm]		
	100	200	300
Ply	100	200	300
Total	0.176	0.198	0.209
CF/epoxy resin	0.142	0.133	0.113
CNT/epoxy resin	0.034	0.065	0.096
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	100-90°	200-90°	300-90°
	100	200	300
Total	0.182	0.185	0.199
CF/epoxy resin	0.144	0.129	0.12
CNT/epoxy resin	0.038	0.056	0.079

Fig. 7 FE-SEM fracture surface images of investigated composite materials

3.3 Tensile properties

3.3.1 CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites

Figure 8 shows stress-strain diagrams of typical CF/CNT/epoxy resin composite samples by tensile test. These stress-strain diagrams indicated linear lines until fracture. Fig. 9 shows average values and standard deviation of elastic modulus. Fig. 10 indicates mean tensile strength of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites. Average elastic modulus, tensile strength and fracture strain of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites are given in Table 2. Fractured area of all most tensile specimens closes to GFRP clamped grips. The results indicated that elastic modulus and tensile strength of the composites decreased with increasing the UD CNT plies. As a result, the reinforcing of CNT sheets in CF direction of prepregs was not improving tensile properties of the composites.

Fig. 8 Stress - strain diagrams of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites

Fig. 9 Elastic modulus of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites

Table 2 Mechanical properties of composites

Plies	0	100	200	300
Elastic modulus [GPa]	137	119	109	104
Tensile strength [MPa]	1548	1514	1072	1050
Fracture strain [%]	1.1	1.3	1.0	1.0

3.3.2 CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composites

Fig. 11 shows stress-strain diagrams of typical tensile specimens of CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composites. These stress-strain diagrams are linear lines until fracture. Average elastic modulus and tensile strength are shown in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13, respectively. Table 3 shows average values of elastic modulus, tensile strength and fracture strain of investigated composites. The results showed that elastic modulus and tensile strength of the composites increased with increasing the CNT plies.

This proved that CNT sheets reinforced in perpendicular direction of CF in the CF/epoxy prepregs improved significantly tensile properties of the composites.

Fig. 10 Tensile strength of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites

Fig. 11 Stress - strain diagrams of CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composites

Fig. 12 Elastic modulus of CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composites

Fig. 13 Tensile strength of CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composites

Table 3 Mechanical properties of composites

Plies	0	100	200	300
Elastic modulus [GPa]	9.1	16.7	21.5	27.6
Tensile strength [MPa]	13.2	19.3	25.5	27.3
Fracture strain [%]	0.14	0.12	0.12	0.10

3.3.3 Elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layers

Fig.14 shows load - strain diagrams of CF/epoxy resin composite (no CNT plies) part and CF/CNT/epoxy resin composite part by tensile test with maximal load of 750 N. At the same strain, the load applied in CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites part is higher than that of CF/epoxy resin composites part. This difference was due to reinforcing of CNT sheet in the composites. Elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layer was calculated from this difference. The following equation is applied to calculate elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layers:

$$E_{CNT/resin} = (A_{CF/CNT/resin} E_{CF/CNT/resin} - A_{CF/resin} E_{CF/resin}) / A_{CNT/resin}$$

E is elastic modulus, A is cross sectional area. Elastic modulus of each CNT/epoxy resin layer was calculated by deducting CF/epoxy resin layer from CF/CNT/epoxy resin layer. Average elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layers is summarized in Table 4. Table 4 proved that elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layers also increased with increasing of UD CNT plies. Then, CNT sheets were responsible for the reinforcement of CNT/epoxy resin composite.

Fig. 14 Load - strain diagrams of investigated composites

Table 4 Elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layers

Plies (-0°)	100	200	300
	46.2	51.7	65.3
Plies (-90°)	100	200	300
	45.3	49.9	55.6

3.4 Thermo gravimetric analysis

The CNT volume fractions of each CNT/epoxy resin layer were calculated from the decrease of sample weight measured by the TGA. In the calculation, it was assumed that all epoxy resin was burned out. After heating, CF/epoxy resin sample was considered to have CF left, and CF/CNT/epoxy resin sample remained only CF and CNT. Table 5 shows weight ratio of CF, CNT and epoxy resin in CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites. After obtaining weight ratio of each component, weight ratio was converted into volume fraction. Table 6 shows volume fraction of ingredients in the composites.

(1) Volume fraction of CNT ranges from 13.4 % (100 plies) to 21.8 % (300 plies). However, epoxy resin was parted in CF/epoxy resin layer or CNT epoxy resin layer. Therefore, volume fraction of epoxy resin was divided into CF/epoxy resin layer or CNT epoxy resin layer by applying layer thickness ratio as shown in Table 1. Table 7 indicates volume fraction of CNT and epoxy resin in CNT/epoxy resin layer.

Fig. 15 Elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layers

3.5 Effective elastic modulus of UD CNT sheet

In each CNT/epoxy resin layer, effective elastic modulus of UD CNT sheet is calculated. The following equation is applied.

$$E_{CNT} = (E_{CNT/resin} \cdot E_{resin} \cdot V_{f_{resin}}) / V_{f_{CNT}} \quad (2)$$

V_f is volume fraction. Table 8 shows effective elastic modulus of UD CNT sheet. The average value of elastic modulus is 144 MPa.

Table 5 Weight ratio of constituent materials

Plies (-0°)	100	200	300
CF	47.9	44.7	42.2
CNT	10.3	16.2	21
Epoxy resin	41.8	39.0	36.8
Plies (-90°)	100	200	300
CF	47.9	45.0	43.4
CNT	13.9	19.1	22.0
Epoxy resin	38.2	35.9	34.6

Table 6 Volume fraction of ingredients in composites

Plies (-0°)	0	100	200	300
CF	46.9	48.2	46.0	44.6
CNT		13.4	17.2	19.9
Epoxy resin	53.1	38.4	36.7	35.6
Plies (-90°)	0	100	200	300
CF	46.9	48.0	45.1	43.5
CNT		13.8	18.9	21.8
Epoxy resin	53.1	38.3	36.0	34.7

Table 7 Volume fraction in CNT/epoxy resin layers

Plies (-0°)	100	200	300
CNT	30.9	35.4	36.6
Epoxy resin	69.1	64.6	63.4
Plies (-90°)	100	200	300
CNT	27.7	41.1	44.5
Epoxy resin	72.3	58.9	55.5

Table 8 Effective elastic modulus of UD CNT sheet

Plies (-0°)	100	200	300
	145	143	175
Plies (-90°)	100	200	300
	158	119	122

In respect of theoretical elastic modulus of pure single CNT in axis direction is reported to be higher than 1.0 TPa. However, elastic modulus of UD CNT sheet in this study was quite low, almost 1/10. This low effective modulus of CNT in this study can be explained by poor stress transfer between CNT layers in MWCNT. Fig.15 shows condition of the tip of broken single CNT. This tip of fractured single CNT is like sword in sheath. Since UD sheet is composed of MWCNTs, just some outer CNT walls supposed to support loads. If UD sheet is composed of MWCNTs with much smaller diameter, effective modulus of MWCNTs in CNT/epoxy resin composites improve.

Fig. 15 FE-SEM fracture surface image of MWCNT

4 Conclusions

CF/CNT/epoxy resin composite materials were produced by superposing UD CNT sheets on CF/epoxy resin prepreg using the autoclave curing. These composite materials were considered as laminates of CF/epoxy resin layer and CNT/epoxy resin layers. The mechanical properties of CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites with different CNT plies in 0 and 90° direction to CF were studied. With increasing the CNT plies, elastic modulus and tensile strength of CF(-0°)/CNT/epoxy resin composites decreased but they increased for CF-90°/CNT/epoxy resin composites. As a result, the reinforcement role of CNT sheet in three phase composites is not high enough in CF direction. Elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layer was successfully calculated by the difference in load - strain diagrams of CF/epoxy resin composite part and CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites part of one specimen. Elastic modulus of CNT/epoxy resin layers ranges from 45.3 MPa (100 plies) to 65.3 MPa (300 plies). Volume fraction of CNT in CF/CNT/epoxy resin composites ranges from 13.4 % (100 plies) to 21.8 % (300 plies). Furthermore, volume fraction of CNT in CNT/epoxy layers varied from 27.7 % (100 plies) to 44.5 % (300 plies). However, effective elastic modulus of UD CNT sheet in these composites is quite low (119 ~ 175 MPa). To increase the mechanical property of MWCNT reinforced composites in this study, usage of MWCNTs with smaller diameter would be effective.

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